

Consumption Propensity as a Factor for Tax Equity of VAT

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Abstract

We evaluate a simulated VAT system with proportionally increased VAT rates regarding horizontal and vertical tax equity for Switzerland. By decomposing the overall redistributive VAT effect on income distribution into a vertical, horizontal and reranking component, we find that ‘unequal treatment of equals’ and ‘reranking of unequals’ do not seem to be major issues. Hence, the concept of horizontal equity is not seriously infringed. We find a reason for this: the consumption propensity mainly differs between, but not within income groups.

Keywords: value added tax; horizontal inequity; reranking; decomposing redistribution

JEL classification: D31; D63; H23; H24; H31

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1. Introduction

Two principles of taxation are horizontal and vertical equity. From a political and tax fairness perspective, aside from the overall redistributive effect of taxation (RE), it is also of interest to decompose RE into a vertical, horizontal and reranking effect (V , H and R). In the context of indirect taxation, H and R might be induced by different consumption patterns, combined with differentiated VAT rates, and different consumption propensities.¹

For Switzerland, Schmutz and Schaltegger (2017) find no statistically significant redistributive effects of a previously existing VAT system on the income Gini coefficient, whereas the effect is statistically significantly regressive with simulated tripled VAT rates. Moreover, they illustrate that different consumption propensities between households might be decisive for the regressive redistributive effect of VAT on income distribution as well as changing the ranking of the households considerably when comparing income with expenditure distribution. However, an analysis regarding vertical and horizontal equity is missing. To close this gap, we decompose RE of this VAT system with simulated tripled VAT rates into different components. Moreover, to explain potential horizontal inequity, we present an approach to analyse to what extent consumption propensities differ between or within income groups.

2. Data and methodology

Extending the analysis of Schmutz and Schaltegger (2017), we also base this paper on data from the Swiss Household Budget Survey ‘Haushaltsbudgeterhebung’ (HABE) for the years 2009 to 2011, compiled by the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (FSO).^{2/3} All data is pooled and weighted⁴ and the theoretical VAT burden per equivalence person is calculated based on tripled VAT rates of those effective from 1 January 2001 on (7.6%; 2.4%; 3.6%) and based on HABE 2009-2011 consumption expenditures.⁵

There are several approaches to decomposing RE ⁶ into different components:

- Kakwani (1984) includes a vertical (V^K) and a horizontal (H^K) effect. Hereby, H^K equates R^{APK} , i.e. the Atkinson-Plotnick-Kakwani reranking index which is based on Atkinson (1980), Plotnick (1981) and Kakwani (1984) and which measures unit reranking because of

¹See, for example, van Doorslaer et al. (1999). However, whether to consider H and R which are caused by different consumption propensities as horizontal inequality is debatable.

²Data source: ‘Bundesamt für Statistik, Haushaltbudgeterhebung (HABE) 2009 bis 2011’.

³See Schmutz and Schaltegger (2017) for further information and references regarding HABE and using household budget survey data for VAT analyses.

⁴The weighting factors are provided by the FSO.

⁵See Schmutz and Schaltegger (2017) for details (further information, references, etc.) such as consumption expenditures definition, VAT rate assignment, VAT shifting to consumer prices and simulation assumptions, exclusion criterion or used (modified) OECD equivalence-scale.

⁶ RE corresponds to pre- minus post-tax Gini coefficient: $RE = G_X - G_{X-T}$ (see Reynolds and Smolensky, 1977, p. 66 f.). For better comprehensibility, we always denote pre-tax by X and post-tax by $X-T$ and also ensure otherwise consistent notation in our paper.

taxation.⁷

- Aronson, Johnson and Lambert (1994) (AJL) include V^{AJL} , H^{AJL} and R^{AJL} : V represents the inequality change if all units per income group paid the same tax rate; H measures the within-group inequality per income group because of taxation (‘unequal treatment of equals’); R results if income groups overlap because of taxation (‘reranking of unequals’).
- van de Ven, Creedy and Lambert (2001) (VCL) include V^{VCL} , H^{VCL} and R^{VCL} . As proposed by Lambert (1995), VCL group the units into ‘close-equals-groups’ (CEG) because normally only a few (or no) units with exactly the same income are included in a micro database (as assumed by AJL).
- Urban and Lambert (2005; 2008) (UL) include V^{UL} , H^{UL} and R^{APK} and considers that R^{APK} might also include reranking of entire CEGs (R^{EG}) and/or reranking within CEGs (R^{WG}): $R^{APK} = R^{AJL} + R^{WG} + R^{EG}$. Accordingly, V^{UL} corresponds to V^{AJL} adjusted for R^{EG} and H^{UL} to H^{AJL} adjusted for R^{WG} .⁸

UL emphasise that the magnitude of (some) decomposition components depends on the choice of CEG bandwidth and propose calculating these components with different bandwidths. VCL already proposed a CEG bandwidth criteria (maximisation of V), which is however only applicable with progressive taxes.

3. Results

Table 1 shows the results of decomposing RE from a simulated VAT system (see Sections 1 and 2). Applying the approach of Kakwani, the share of the reranking effect (R^{APK}) on RE amounts to just over 12 percent. Applying the VCL approach, we find, as expected, that R^{VCL} is smaller compared to R^{APK} , because R^{VCL} neglects reranking of entire groups (R^{EG}) and within group reranking (R^{WG}). Accordingly, R^{VCL} is highest using narrow CEG bandwidths and tends towards zero as CEG bandwidths increase and reranking between CEGs becomes less likely. In contrast, H^{VCL} is smallest with narrow CEG bandwidths and increases with increasing CEG bandwidths. Interestingly, H^{VCL} and R^{VCL} account together for about 11 to 13 percent of RE for all CEG bandwidths from CHF 10 to 1000, because the effects of R^{WG} and R^{VCL} approximately offset each other as CEG bandwidths change. It takes unreasonably large CEG bandwidths (e.g. of CHF 5000) to increase the horizontal at the expense of the vertical effect. The results from the UL approach confirm our findings: V^{UL} corresponds approximately to V^{VCL} , because R^{EG} only exists with small CEG bandwidths and H^{UL} , which adjusts H^{VCL} for R^{WG} , becomes negligible, given reasonable CEG bandwidths.

⁷See, i.e., Urban and Lambert (2008).

⁸We base our calculation of V^{UL} and H^{UL} on the components according to VCL, since we use CEGs.

To summarise, the overwhelming majority of RE is because of the vertical effect – provided reasonable CEGs are used.

Table 1
Splitting the redistributive VAT effect RE into different components

Kakwani						
V^K	87.64%					
R^{APK}	12.36%					
	CEG bandwidth in CHF					
	10	100	500	1000	5000	10000
VCL						
V^{VCL}	88.72%	87.66%	87.68%	87.39%	78.64%	53.99%
H^{VCL}	0.26%	2.28%	6.92%	9.58%	20.72%	45.89%
R^{VCL}	11.02%	10.07%	5.39%	3.03%	0.63%	0.12%
UL						
V^{UL}	87.41%	87.63%	87.68%	87.39%	78.64%	53.99%
H^{UL}	0.23%	0.00%	-0.05%	0.25%	8.99%	33.64%
R^{APK}	12.36%	12.36%	12.36%	12.36%	12.36%	12.36%
R^{VCL}	11.02%	10.07%	5.39%	3.03%	0.63%	0.12%
R^{EG}	1.31%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
R^{WG}	0.03%	2.27%	6.97%	9.33%	11.73%	12.25%

Notes: All figures in percent of RE . $RE = G_X - G_{X-T}$ ($-0.00752 = 0.27910 - 0.28662$).

Source: Own calculation based on weighed HABE data 2009-2011.

If all households had identical consumption propensities, the Gini coefficient of gross income and the concentration coefficient of consumption expenditures (ranking by gross income) would be identical. Therefore, the difference between these two measures is attributable to different consumption propensities between households (Schmutz and Schaltegger, 2017). To investigate whether the consumption propensities mainly differ between or within CEGs, we split the difference between the equalised gross income Gini coefficient and the equalised consumption expenditure concentration coefficient (ranking by gross income)⁹ into two components: one measuring the share of the overall difference caused by different consumption propensities between CEGs ($G_{inc}^B - C_{exp}^B$), and the other measuring the share caused by different consumption propensities within CEGs ($G_{inc}^W - C_{exp}^W$):¹⁰

$$G_{inc} - C_{exp} = (G_{inc}^B - C_{exp}^B) + (G_{inc}^W - C_{exp}^W) \quad (1)$$

Table 2 shows that with a reasonable CEG bandwidth of CHF 100 equalised gross income, and even with a large CEG bandwidth of CHF 1000, the effect of different consumption propensities within CEGs is negligible compared to the effect between CEGs.

⁹This coefficient is calculated with equalised consumption expenditures including single VAT, because we assume no effect of tripling VAT rates on relative consumption propensities.

¹⁰ C_{exp}^B is adjusted for R^{EG} and C_{exp}^W for R^{WG} .

Table 2*Comparing the impact of different consumption propensities within vs. between income groups*

	CEG bandwidth in CHF			
	100		1000	
	absolute	in percent*	absolute	in percent*
$G_{inc} - C_{exp}$	0.11031	100.00%	0.11031	100.00%
$G_{inc}^B - C_{exp}^B$	0.11075	100.39%	0.10957	99.32%
$G_{inc}^W - C_{exp}^W$	-0.00043	0.39%	0.00075	0.68%

Notes: *in percent of $G_{inc} - C_{exp}$. inc = equivalised gross income pre-VAT. exp = equivalised consumption expenditures including (single) VAT.

Source: Own calculation based on weighted HABE data 2009-2011.

4. Conclusion

Our results show that, given reasonable CEGs, an overwhelming share of the overall redistributive effect of the simulated VAT system on income can be attributed to the vertical component. In contrast, the horizontal and reranking components are moderate, even together: neither ‘unequal treatment of equals’, nor ‘reranking of unequals’ are serious issues in the Swiss VAT system, even with largely and proportionally increased VAT rates. As a factor for the low horizontal component, i.e. H^{UL} , we identify that consumption propensities mainly differ between households from different income groups as opposed to within income groups.

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